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Barriers to Institutional AI Integration: A Systematic Approach Using FUCOM and Segmentation Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies promise revolutionary transformations in many areas, from decision-making processes to service delivery within the public sector. However, despite this potential, the effective utilization of AI at institutional and societal levels in the public sector faces significant barriers. Multi-layered challenges such as deficiencies in technological infrastructure, concerns about data security and privacy, ethical uncertainties, employee resistance, inadequate legal and administrative frameworks, and limited organizational learning capacity constitute major barriers to the widespread adoption of AI applications. This study analyses the primary barriers to AI utilization in public institutions through a holistic and systematic perspective. It identifies and prioritizes these barriers using the Full Consistency Method (FUCOM), a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) approach based on expert judgment. After weighting the barriers, decision-makers within public sector organizations are clustered using segmentation analysis based on their professional profiles and contextual characteristics, thereby revealing resistance patterns and varying levels of institutional readiness in more detail. The findings indicate that, beyond technical and infrastructural limitations, cognitive, ethical, and institutional factors also contribute to delays in AI integration. Moreover, the study demonstrates that decision-makers' and managers' perceptions of AI significantly influence both the severity and nature of these barriers. Drawing on both the literature and empirical data, the study proposes strategic recommendations to overcome these barriers and discusses the governance structures necessary for the sustainable dissemination of AI applications. In addition, by combining methodological rigor with practical insight, this study offers evidence-based recommendations to address the challenges hindering the systematic deployment of AI and highlights the governance approaches essential for overcoming future adaptation constraints.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) technologies have emerged as an indispensable transformation tool in public administration, alongside modern technologies such as cloud computing, the Internet of Things (IoT) and big data. The growing adoption of AI in the public sector enhances administrative efficiency, accelerates service delivery, supports decision-making processes,

and improves citizen satisfaction [1]. Particularly in areas such as the automation of routine tasks and the simplification of complex processes, AI offers significant potential to enhance the quality and effectiveness of public services [2].

However, the adoption and dissemination of AI in public administration face significant challenges such as technological infrastructure deficiencies, data security concerns and legal uncertainties [3, 4]. These challenges limit the full realization of AI's potential benefits and slow down the innovative transformation of public services. In addition, human related factors, such as staff resistance to AI technologies and insufficient technical knowledge, pose additional barriers to institutional adaptation [5, 6]. The limited financial resources of public institutions represent another significant barrier to investments in AI [4].

The literature emphasizes the need for a systematic analysis of the factors influencing the adoption of AI applications in public administration [7]. The successful integration of AI into the public sector requires multidimensional strategies such as increasing awareness of technology, making infrastructure investments, strengthening personnel training, and clarifying legal and regulatory frameworks [8].

In this context, the present study aims to examine the barriers affecting the adoption and dissemination of AI in public administration with a holistic approach. To this end, the barriers identified through a literature review and expert opinions were weighted using the Full Consistency Method (FUCOM), one of the Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) method. Furthermore, the dataset was segmented using the K-means clustering algorithm to conduct a segment analysis. This allowed the identification of barriers that were perceived as highly influential or relatively insignificant by different groups. These groupings were also interpreted based on the decision-makers' years of professional experience. Accordingly, the study proposes strategic priorities and governance structures necessary for achieving a sustainable and effective digital transformation in public institutions.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. The Methodology section introduces the Full Consistency Method (FUCOM) and the segmentation analysis approach, which were used to evaluate and classify the barriers to AI adoption. The Application section outlines the construction of the MCDM model, the process of calculating criteria weights using FUCOM, and the implementation of K-means clustering for segment analysis. The Findings and Discussion section presents the results obtained from the analysis and discusses their implications in relation to the institutional characteristics of the identified segments.

2 METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodological framework employed in the study. First, the Full Consistency Method (FUCOM) is utilized to determine the relative importance of barriers to AI adoption based on expert judgments. Then, segmentation analysis using the K-means clustering algorithm is conducted to classify decision-makers into distinct groups according to their perceptions and professional profiles. The combined use of these methods allows for both the prioritization of key barriers and the identification of differentiated patterns across respondent segments.

2.1 The Full Consistency Method (FUCOM)

The Full Consistency Method (FUCOM) is a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) method that aims to determine the weights of criteria using expert judgments or statistical data. Originally introduced by Pamučar et al. [9], the method has since been applied in a variety of decision-making contexts, including forklift selection [10] sustainable supplier selection [11,12], distribution channel selection [13,14], human resource management [15], and health performance management [16]. FUCOM stands out from other weighting methods by requiring fewer pairwise comparisons.

Specifically, it enables solution generation through only $n - 1$ comparisons for n criteria, thereby improving efficiency without compromising consistency [17].

The FUCOM method consists of three main computational steps, which are outlined below [9, 17]:

Step 1: The first step involves ranking the evaluation criteria from the predefined set $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}$. The criteria are ranked based on their significance, which means that the criteria with the highest weight coefficient is ranked first, followed by the criterion with the lowest relevance. As a result, the criteria are sorted based on the weight coefficients' predicted values:

$$C_{j(1)} > C_{j(2)} > \dots > C_{j(k)} \tag{1}$$

where $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ is the rank of the criterion that is detected. When two or more criteria are judged to have the same significance, the equality symbol is used in place of the ">" between them in the Eq. (1).

Step 2: In the second step, the ranking criteria are compared, and the evaluation criteria's comparative priority $\varphi_{k/(k+1)}$ is established. The evaluation criteria's vectors of comparative priorities are thus obtained, as shown in the Eq. (2).

$$\Phi = (\varphi_{1/2}, \varphi_{2/3}, \varphi_{3/4}, \dots, \varphi_{k/(k+1)}) \tag{2}$$

where the value $\varphi_{k/(k+1)}$ indicates that the $C_{j(k)}$ rank criterion is superior to the $C_{j(k+1)}$ rank. The decision-maker(s) may compare criteria using decimals, integers, or values from specific scales. This gives decision-maker(s) flexibility when assessing the criteria.

Step 3: The final values of the weight coefficients of the evaluation criteria $(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ are computed in the third step. The weight coefficients' final values must meet the following two requirements:

- The comparative priority of the criteria established in Step 2 is equal to the ratio of the weight coefficients provided in Eq. (3).

$$\frac{w_k}{w_{k+1}} = \varphi_{k/(k+1)} \tag{3}$$

- The final values of the weight coefficients should meet the requirements of mathematical transitivity, which means $\varphi_{k/(k+1)} \otimes \varphi_{(k+1)/(k+2)} = \varphi_{k/(k+2)}$. Since $\varphi_{k/(k+1)} = \frac{w_k}{w_{k+1}}$ and $\varphi_{(k+1)/(k+2)} = \frac{w_{k+1}}{w_{k+2}}$, that $\frac{w_k}{w_{k+1}} \otimes \frac{w_{k+1}}{w_{k+2}} = \frac{w_k}{w_{k+2}}$ is obtained. Consequently, the final values of the weight coefficients of the evaluation criteria must satisfy yet another requirement, which is as follows:

$$\frac{w_k}{w_{k+2}} = \varphi_{k/(k+1)} \otimes \varphi_{(k+1)/(k+2)} \tag{4}$$

When the requirements in the Eq. (3) and Eq. (4) are met, full consistency is confirmed. Specifically, in this instance, the deviation from full consistency (DFC) is minimal. DFC is $\mathcal{X} = 0$ for the computed values of the weight coefficients, hence satisfying the maximal consistency condition.

The degree of *DFC* (χ) and the final values of the evaluation criteria $(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ are produced by solving the linear programming model presented in Eq. (5).

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Min } \chi \\
 & \left| \frac{w_{j(k)}}{w_{j(k+1)}} - \varphi_{k/(k+1)} \right| \leq \chi, \forall j \\
 & \left| \frac{w_{j(k)}}{w_{j(k+2)}} - \varphi_{k/(k+1)} \otimes \varphi_{(k+1)/(k+2)} \right| \leq \chi, \forall j \\
 & \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1 \\
 & w_j \geq 0, \forall j
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

2.2 Segmentation Analysis

Segmentation analysis is a statistical method used to classify a dataset into subgroups, known as segments. These segments are internally homogeneous but externally heterogeneous, and are formed based on shared characteristics or behavioural patterns. This method is frequently employed in disciplines such as marketing, strategic management, and the social sciences. Segmentation analysis facilitates a deeper understanding of variability in perceptions, preferences, or decision-making processes, thereby allowing researchers to tailor interventions or strategies according to the distinct needs of each identified group [18].

Segmentation analysis encompasses several types, each based on different classification criteria. Behavioural segmentation groups individuals according to their purchasing habits and product usage patterns, while demographic segmentation relies on attributes such as age, gender, and income. Psychographic segmentation focuses on attitudes, values, and lifestyles. Geographic segmentation classifies consumers based on their location, such as region, city, or country. Lastly, corporate segmentation targets organizations, grouping them by size, industry, or managerial characteristics [19].

Segment analysis enables businesses and researchers to develop customized strategies by gaining deeper insights into their target groups. Thus, resources are used more effectively and efficiently. By facilitating the prediction of customer or user behaviour, it supports more accurate decision-making and increases satisfaction and loyalty through solutions tailored to the needs of different groups. In this way, it improves operational efficiency in marketing and management activities and strengthens institutions' ability to achieve a competitive advantage [20, 21].

3 APPLICATION

3.1 Forming a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Model

Based on expert opinions and literature review, fifteen critical barriers to the adoption and integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in public administration were identified as evaluation criteria. These barriers are: (C1) high installation and maintenance costs, (C2) insufficient funding and resource allocation, (C3) lack of long-term strategic planning for AI applications, (C4) lack of staff skills and knowledge in the field of AI, (C5) employee resistance to change, (C6) absence of effective leadership, (C7) inadequate infrastructure and legacy systems, (C8) problems in data collection and management, (C9) cybersecurity and data protection issues, (C10) legal uncertainties, (C11) concerns regarding bias and accountability, (C12) violation of personal data protection rights, (C13) excessive bureaucratic procedures, (C14) lack of inter-institutional integration, and (C15)

uncertainty about how AI algorithms function. These criteria constitute the input variables of the FUCOM method.

3.2 Determining the Weights of Criteria Using the FUCOM Method

The 15 identified barriers were presented to 16 decision-makers working in the public sector, who were asked to evaluate their impact on hindering AI implementation using a 5-point Likert scale. In this scale, 1 indicates “ineffective”, 2 “slightly effective”, 3 “neither effective nor ineffective”, 4 “effective”, and 5 “very effective”.

Step 1: Each barrier was ranked according to the average score it received from decision makers. Accordingly; (C7) inadequate infrastructure and legacy systems have the highest average with 4.625, while (C15) uncertainty about how AI algorithms function has the lowest average with 3.5625. The overall ranking obtained is as follows:

$$C7 > C8 > C9 > C12 > C14 = C3 > C1 = C10 > C2 = C11 > C5 = C13 > C6 > C4 > C15$$

Step 2: The relative importance of each criterion compared to the previous one was calculated. Thus, comparative priorities (φ_k) were obtained as given.

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{c7/c8} &= \frac{4.625}{4.5625} = 1.0137 & \varphi_{c8/c9} &= \frac{4.5625}{4.375} = 1.0429 & \varphi_{c9/c12} &= \frac{4.375}{4.25} = 1.0294 \\ \varphi_{c12/c14} &= \frac{4.25}{4.125} = 1.0303 & \varphi_{c14/c3} &= \frac{4.125}{4.125} = 1 & \varphi_{c3/c1} &= \frac{4.125}{4.0625} = 1.0154 \\ \varphi_{c1/c10} &= \frac{4.0625}{4.0625} = 1 & \varphi_{c10/c2} &= \frac{4.0625}{3.9375} = 1.0317 & \varphi_{c2/c11} &= \frac{3.9375}{3.9375} = 1 \\ \varphi_{c11/c5} &= \frac{3.9375}{3.8125} = 1.0328 & \varphi_{c5/c13} &= \frac{3.8125}{3.8125} = 1 & \varphi_{c13/c6} &= \frac{3.8125}{3.75} = 1.0167 \\ \varphi_{c6/c4} &= \frac{3.75}{3.6875} = 1.0169 & \varphi_{c4/c15} &= \frac{3.6875}{3.5625} = 1.0351 \end{aligned}$$

Step 3: The following linear model were taken into account to calculate the final values of the weighting coefficients.

Min χ

$$\left| \frac{w_7}{w_8} - 1.0137 \right| \leq \chi, \left| \frac{w_8}{w_9} - 1.0429 \right| \leq \chi, \left| \frac{w_7}{w_8} - 1.0137 \right| \leq \chi, \dots, \left| \frac{w_4}{w_{15}} - 1.0351 \right| \leq \chi$$

$$\left| \frac{w_7}{w_9} - 1.0137 \otimes 1.0429 \right| \leq \chi, \dots, \left| \frac{w_6}{w_{15}} - 1.0169 \otimes 1.0351 \right| \leq \chi,$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$$

$$w_j \geq 0, \forall j$$

By solving this model by Excel Solver, the final values of the weight coefficients presented in Table 1 was obtained. $\sum w = 1$ and maximum $DCF(\chi) = 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$, which means the “full consistency” condition is met in practice.

Table 1 The Weight Coefficients for Each Barrier

#	Criterion	w_k
C7	Inadequate infrastructure and legacy systems	0.07621
C8	Problems in data collection and management	0.07518
C9	Cybersecurity and data protection issues	0.07209
C12	Violation of personal data protection rights	0.070031
C14	Lack of inter-institutional integration	0.067971
C3	Lack of long-term strategic planning for AI applications	0.067971
C1	High installation and maintenance costs	0.066941
C10	Legal uncertainties	0.066941
C2	Insufficient funding and resource allocation	0.064882
C11	Concerns regarding bias and accountability	0.064882
C5	Employee resistance to change	0.062822
C13	Excessive bureaucratic procedures	0.062822
C6	Absence of effective leadership	0.061792
C4	Lack of staff skills and knowledge in the field of AI	0.060762
C15	Uncertainty about how AI algorithms function	0.058702

As a result, according to the perception of decision makers, the most dominant barrier to AI adoption in the public sector is “Inadequate Infrastructure and Legacy Systems” with a weight of 7.62%. In contrast, the “Uncertainty about how AI algorithms function” has the lowest impact on AI adoption in the public sector with a weight of 5.87%.

3.3 Segmentation Analysis with K-Means Clustering Approach

In order to explore distinct profiles among public sector decision-makers regarding their perceptions of barriers to artificial intelligence (AI) adoption, a segmentation analysis was conducted using the K-Means clustering algorithm. This unsupervised learning method enables the identification of homogeneous groups based on shared patterns in Likert-scale evaluations across multiple barriers. Two complementary methods, the Elbow Method and the Silhouette Score, were used to identify the ideal number of clusters (k) before the clustering process was put into action.

The Elbow Method involves plotting the within-cluster sum of squares (WCSS) for varying values of k and identifying the point at which the rate of decrease sharply changes, suggesting a balance between model complexity and explained variance. In parallel, the Silhouette Score was computed for each k to evaluate the cohesion and separation of clusters. This metric ranges from -1 to +1, with higher values indicating more distinct and well-formed clusters. The results of the both techniques were shown in Figure 1.

Figure1: (a) Elbow Method Results (b) Silhouette Score Results

Both techniques indicated that a three-cluster structure ($k = 3$) would provide the most meaningful segmentation. Based on this finding, a K-Means clustering analysis was performed to classify the decision makers into three distinct segments. These clusters were then analyzed to interpret the variations in AI barrier perceptions among public sector professionals, providing valuable insight into differentiated readiness and resistance profiles within the sample.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To better understand how public sector decision-makers perceive the barriers to adopting AI, a segmentation analysis was conducted using the K-Means clustering method. Based on the Elbow Method and Silhouette Score, it was determined that a three-cluster solution would be the most appropriate. Accordingly, participants were grouped into three segments with distinct barrier perception profiles.

Segment 1 – Infrastructure and Organizational Focused (Cluster 1): Participants in this segment assigned the highest importance to practical and operational issues, such as inadequate infrastructure, data collection and management problems, and resistance to change. On the other hand, they rated legal uncertainty, data security, and privacy concerns as less important. This group had the highest average professional experience (21.5 years), which may explain their greater focus on implementation-level problems.

These findings show that the segment in question has a managerial profile that focuses more on technical applications and favors practical solution approaches. These managers, who have developed an awareness based on experience about the barriers encountered in practice, prioritize operational infrastructure, organizational transformation and internal dynamics in their decision-making processes. In addition, their experience makes them strong candidates for leading pilot projects and infrastructure modernization efforts.

Segment 2 – Balanced Concern Group (Cluster 2): This group gave relatively high and balanced ratings to all categories of barriers. They were concerned with both technical (infrastructure, leadership, integration) and systemic (privacy, cybersecurity, legal issues) barriers. Their average experience was 18 years.

This segment stands out with its capacity to assess multi-faceted risks. Aware of both practical and systemic barriers, these decision-makers simultaneously draw attention to the multi-dimensional organization of comprehensive digital public policies and the harmonization between institutions and legal regulations. Evaluating the technical, administrative and ethical dimensions of digital options

together, this group has the potential to play a “balancing” and “bridging” role in the broad scope of reforms.

Segment 3 – Legal and Security Focused (Cluster 3): The third segment showed the highest concern for legal uncertainty, data protection, and cybersecurity. In contrast, they gave relatively low ratings to installation costs and bureaucratic issues. This group had the lowest average experience (16.6 years) and may represent younger professionals who are more sensitive to ethical and legal aspects of digital systems.

This segment represents the rising managerial actors of the digital age. These individuals are especially focused on transparency, accountability, and regulatory compliance in AI use. Their priorities reflect growing concerns in the public sector about digital rights and secure implementation. This group is expected to contribute to normative regulations and digital security rather than institutional transformation.

5 CONCLUSION

This study aimed to systematically examine the key barriers hindering the adoption of AI in public sector institutions by combining the FUCOM with segmentation analysis. Through expert evaluations and quantitative modelling, the research prioritized fifteen critical barriers and classified public sector decision-makers based on their perceptions and professional profiles. This integrated approach not only highlights the most influential barriers but also reveals how perceptions of these challenges vary across different segments. Therefore, this study contributes to both theoretical understanding and practical road mapping efforts for AI-driven digital transformation in the public sector.

The weights obtained with the FUCOM method clearly revealed the priority map of the factors that prevent the widespread adoption of AI applications in the public sector. The findings indicate that the total weight of the first five barriers approaches 36% ($w \approx 0.362$), creating a significantly greater impact compared to the remaining barriers.

Infrastructure inadequacy and legacy systems ($w = 0.076$) emerge as the most critical barriers, indicating the urgent need to digital transformation investments with modern and scalable IT architectures. Data collection and management issues ($w = 0.075$) emphasize that improving data governance and quality is not only a technical task but also a strategic imperative. In addition, cybersecurity and data protection risks ($w = 0.072$) and concerns about personal data breaches ($w = 0.070$) have a share of over 14% in total weight, revealing the key importance of trust-centered architecture and regulatory compliance. Finally the lack of a long-term artificial intelligence strategy ($w = 0.068$) shows that the lack of a clear corporate vision is as decisive as technical deficiencies in hindering AI adoption.

This distribution proves that the barriers for AI adoption are not limited to technical infrastructure; dimensions such as data governance, security and privacy, and strategic planning are interdependent and equally critical. Therefore, the priority step is to modernize outdated systems with an integrated digital transformation program and to restructure the data infrastructure according to institutional standards. Simultaneously, cybersecurity protocols and compliance processes related to KVKK/GDPR must be strengthened, which will increase stakeholder trust and encourage participation in data sharing and AI initiatives. Finally, a medium to long term national or institutional AI roadmap should be developed and this roadmap should connect technical investments, legislative updates and change management strategies within a unified framework.

In short, the FUCOM analysis provides organizations a clear answer to the question “where should we start?” and confirms that a holistic approach that simultaneously addresses technical modernization, data security and strategic governance is essential for achieving sustainable digital transformation.

The segmentation analysis also shows a clear relationship between experience levels and the types of barriers perceived as most important. As experience increased, participants tended to focus more on infrastructure and organizational challenges. Those with less experience placed greater emphasis on legal, ethical, and data protection issues. Therefore, digital transformation strategies in the public sector must consider not only organizational needs but also differences in generational perspectives and expertise levels. This finding suggests that digital transformation initiatives in public institutions should be designed to the specific characteristics and needs of the target group.

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